

The moderating role of self-control on the relationship between opportunity, job pressure and employee deviance

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Abstract

This study examines self-control as a moderator in the relationships amongst the dimensions of opportunity (institutional policy and ethical climate), job pressure (excessive workload and job pressure), and deviant workplace behaviour (interpersonal and organizational deviance) among lecturers. The study employed survey instruments to obtain data from faculty members in Nigerian public universities. More so, variance-based structural equation modeling was employed to run analysis on 536 questionnaires filled by faculty members in public universities in Nigeria. Statistical results indicate that self-control significantly moderates the relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance. Also, self-control moderates the relationship between workload and organizational deviance as well as the relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance. In conclusion, self-control is a veritable tool to restrain deviant acts even when there are opportunity and pressure to commit unethical acts. Hence, administrators of public universities may consider the level of self-control of would-be faculty members during recruitment exercise. Practical and theoretical implications are discussed including limitations of study.

Keywords: Institutional policy, ethical climate, excessive workload, work pressure, self-control, organizational and interpersonal deviance.

Introduction

Robinson (2008) found that negative deviance has severe impacts on organizations and its stakeholders and such negative impacts include decreased productivity (Martin & Hine, 2005), work-related stress (Hakanen, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2006), damaged organization's reputation (Bowling & Gruys, 2010), and decreased profitability (Lee & Ok, 2014). Also, deviant workplace behaviour (DWB) has been associated with negative antecedents, such as organizational injustice (Ambrose, Seabright, & Schminke, 2002; Henle, 2005), negative affectivity (Aquino, Grover, Bradfield, & Allen, 1999) and psychological contract breach (Bordia, Restubog, & Tang, 2008). However, past studies have placed little consideration on the impact of opportunity-centred factors in predicting DWB. To reduce this gap, we asked a major question which many researchers have not asked: what factors stimulate and sustain negative deviant workplace behaviour among faculty members? The answer to this question linked individual characteristics to perception of institutional policies and prevailing climates in the universities. We argue that when opportunities exist in the forms of poor ethical climate and poor perception of institutional policy, then deviance may thrive. Our argument is buttressed by theory of crime (Gottfredson & Hirschi, 1990), which

posits that criminal acts are often markedly non-controlled; they are both opportunistic and short-sighted. Although limited studies exist on ethical climate, they are not specifically related to workplace deviance.

In reality, teaching is a stressful occupation because of emotional demands, large class sizes, inadequate resources, high workload, inadequate salary, and pressure to attract external funding for publications, role conflict, student negative deviant behaviour and the perceived low status of the profession (Hakanen, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2006). In Nigerian context, the job pressure on academics is considered to be high probably due to the level of development and specifically the amount of academic workload, poor salary package and work pressure involved (NEEDS Report, 2012; Omolayo & Omole, 2013). Notwithstanding, past studies have failed to establish empirical relationship between workload, work pressure and negative behaviours among academics.

Generally, academics enjoy a reasonable level of autonomy, but how do faculty members strike a balance between autonomy and negative deviance? This is where individual's level of self-control comes to play. Past studies have considered self-control in relation to revenge (Bordia, Tang, & Restubog, 2008), trait of anger, and negative reciprocity beliefs (Restubog, Garcia, Wang & Cheng, 2010). Studies reported that self-control has the tendency to override negative deviance (Bordia, Tang, & Restubog, 2008; Restubog, Garcia, Wang & Cheng, 2010) but studies on the role of self-control as a moderator in the links between opportunity-centred factors and DWB among lecturers are lacking. Our position on self-control is supported by general theory of crime, otherwise referred to as theory of self-control (Gottfredson & Hirschi, 1990). Therefore, the present study wishes to find out empirically whether self-control can strengthen or diminish the proposed relationships amongst the constructs.

Conceptual Review and Hypotheses Development

Workplace deviance

Workplace deviance is basically categorized into constructive/positive and negative deviance. Constructive deviance is defined as a voluntary behaviour that violates significant organizational norms and in doing so contributes to the well-being of an organization, its members, or both" (Galperin, 2003). Examples of such behaviours include among others: departing from the organisational norms to solve problems and using unconventional ways to achieve work goals (Galperin, 2003, 2012; Kura, Shamsudin, & Chauhan, 2016). On the other hand, Robinson and Bennett (1995) described negative deviant workplace behaviour (DWB) as a deliberate behaviour which breaks the norms of organizations significantly and harms organizational well-being, the well-being of its workforce or both.

Organizational deviance includes all forms of unethical behaviours exhibited by the employees towards the organizations or its assets while those deviant acts whose primary targets are colleagues, students and other organizational members is regarded as interpersonal deviance (Bennett & Robinson, 2000).

Opportunity

Osgood, Wilson, O'Malley, Bachman, and Johnson (1996) pointed out that the motivation to commit any deviant act depends on the level of situational opportunities created by routine activities. Extant literature revealed that less emphasis has been focused on the effects of opportunity-centred antecedents of DWB such as ethical climate and perception of institutional policy. Therefore, we argue that opportunities in the

forms of poor ethical climate and perceived weak institutional policy can make deviance thrive. Also, this argument agrees with the facet of opportunity in fraud triangle theory (FTT) which states that weakness in internal conditions of an organization creates opportunity for unethical acts (Cressey, 1950). Furthermore, Simha and Cullen (2012) re-echoed the submission of Martin and Cullen (2006) when they called for empirical studies to diagnose the relationship between ethical climates and unethical behaviours which have remained largely under-researched. Heeding these calls, we focused on ethical climate and perception of institutional policy as predictors of deviant behaviours among academicians.

Ethical climate and DWB

Ethical climate (EC) is the perception of right behaviour and psychological mechanisms by which ethical issues are judged (Victor & Cullen, 1988; Simha & Cullen, 2012). Vardi (2001) examined the influence of ethical climates on misbehaviours at work. The study used 97 samples from production, marketing and administration sections of a manufacturing plant in Israel. The study found a significant negative association between organizational misbehaviour and organizational climate and between climate dimensions and organizational misbehaviour. Furthermore, in 2002, Peterson found that the association between unethical behaviour and ethical climate is stronger in organizations without a code of ethics. Fraud triangle theory's facet of opportunity posited that the innate vulnerability of the firm to manipulation makes it susceptible to deviance. Also, when academics perceive ill-treatment in the work climate and absence of ethical codes, then deviance may thrive (Cressey, 1950). Based on social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), if there is sound ethical climate favourable to faculty members they will not engage in negative deviance. Also, theory of self-control agrees that if there is weak ethical climate while lecturers possess high level of self-control, negative deviance will not surface. Therefore, we hypothesized as follows:

H1: There will be a negative relationship between perceived ethical climate and organizational deviance among academics.

H2: There will be a negative relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance.

Perception of institutional policy and DWB

Institutional policy has been conceptualized as the policies that govern an institution's relationships with its main components -faculty members and students. In reality, many acts of deviance, crimes and adolescent delinquency have been traced to routine activity approach. This approach posits that opportunities that arise in routine, everyday life are crucial in explaining DWB and crimes (Cohen & Felson, 1979). To a reasonable extent, teaching is a routine activity and if the internal mechanisms within HEIs are weak, it can encourage deviance. Hence, when ethical climate and policy of HEIs are poorly perceived, the resultant effect may be DWB.

Practically, management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria have adopted several institutional-level interventions to minimize negative deviance but they have not been particularly effective. For example, many institutions have inaugurated committees on decent conduct, anti-corruption campaigns, staff disciplinary committees, honour and integrity awards but these initiatives cannot bring about desired change unless there are effective institutional changes (Cole & McCabe, 1996).

Extant literature and theoretical views attempted to establish a negative relationship between effective institutional policies and DWB. Cheng et al. (2013) confirmed that perception of formal sanction was significantly linked to information systems security violation behaviours. General deterrence theory-GDT (Beccaria, 1963; Gibbs, 1968) fundamentally postulates that employees will be discouraged from indulging in negative deviant acts when the penance for an unethical engagement is assured and painful. Also, social exchange theory postulates that if academics perceive institutional policies to be partial, discriminatory and unfriendly towards them, negative deviance may arise. Hence:

H3: There will be a negative relationship between perception of institutional policy and organizational deviance.

H4: There will be a negative relationship between perception of institutional policy and interpersonal deviance.

Job pressure

Although most jobs have associated stress but faculty members experience more pressure to meet deadline regarding teaching, research, and community services (Houston, Meyer & Paewei, 2006). In the present study, job pressure is considered as having two dimensions namely academic workload and work pressure (Houston et al., 2006). Academic workload is operationalized as the professional efforts lecturers dedicate to tasks such as research, teaching, and community services while work pressure is conceptualized as the degree to which an academic has to work fast and hard, has a great deal to do, but with too little time (Karasek & Theorell, 1990).

Academic workload, Work pressure and DWB

In Nigerian context, the job pressure on academics is considered to be on the extreme due to the amount of academic workload, poor salary package and work pressure involved (NEEDS report, 2012). This stress level has impacts on job satisfaction, commitment, engagement and employees' behaviours at work ((Hakanen, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2006).

Empirically, workload and work pressure have been found to be negatively related to job satisfaction and work engagement among faculty members in public HEIs (Rothmann & Jordaan, 2006; Shahzad, Mumtaz, Hayat & Khan, 2010). If these findings hold, then both workload and work pressure would be veritable tools to predict negative deviance among academics.

Practically, when lecturers experience excessive workload and pressure at work, the resultant effects might be deviance because social exchange theory posits that perception of inequality between efforts and reward will lead to negative behaviour from employees in form of deviance. This position is supported by effort-reward-imbalance model. Hence, we state thus:

H5: Workload is positively related to organizational deviance among academics.

H6: Workload will be positively related to interpersonal deviance among academics.

H7: There will be a positive relationship between work pressure and organizational deviance.

H8: There will be a positive relationship between work pressure and interpersonal deviance.

Self-control as a moderator between ethical climate, institutional policy and DWB

Studies by Ambrose, Arnaud and Schminke (2008) found that ethical climates promote ethical behaviours when collective empathy and collective ethical efficacy levels are high. In relation to DWB, Bulutlar and Oz (2009) found a significant relationship between ethical climate dimensions, bullying behaviour and organizational commitment in Turkey. Mead, Baumeister, Gino, Schweitzer, and Ariely (2009) reported that employees are likely to falsify their production output for monetary benefits whenever their self-control resources diminished. In agreement with theory of self-control, Bordia, Restubog, and Tang (2008) demonstrated that employees who have higher self-control are less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors. Also, theory of crime (Hirschi & Gottfredson, 1990) posits that employee low in self-control is a potential deviant and wrongdoer than those high in self-regulation when there is an opportunity.

According to self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1997), individuals low in self-regulatory efficacy have higher tendency to participate in deviant behaviours unlike employees with higher levels of self-regulatory efficacy. In practice, academics high in self-control will not engage in negative deviance even if they perceive weaknesses in institutional policy or consider ethical climate as ineffective but same cannot be said of lecturers with low level of self-control. Based on past empirics, practice and theoretical views, we hypothesize thus:

H9: Self-control moderates the relationship between ethical climate and organizational deviance among academics. The relationship is stronger (more negative) for academics with high level of self-control than those with low level of self-control.

H10: Self-control will moderate the relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance among academics. The relationship will be weaker (more positive) for an individual low in self-control than those high in self-control.

H11: Self-control moderates the relationship between institutional policy and organizational deviance among academics. The relationship is stronger (more negative) for academics high in self-control than those low in self-control.

H12: Self-control will moderate the relationship between perception of institutional policy and interpersonal deviance among academics. The relationship is stronger (more negative) for academics high in self-control than those low in self-control.

Self-control as a moderator between workload, work pressure and DWB

In the present setting, self-control is a resource which enables academics to refrain from engaging in undesired acts. Faculty members exert self-control when they follow rules or inhibit desires to collect gratifications. Without self-control, academics would accept gratifications or respond positively to unethical acts but self-control resources can be depleted if over-stretched (Muraven & Baumeister, 2000).

Self-control theory posits that a person who scored low in self-control have higher tendency to participate in criminal and delinquent behaviours than those high in self-control. Logically, academicians with high level of self-control may refuse to react positively towards stressful work situations but the same cannot be said of faculty members with low level of self-control. Based on social exchange theory, employees

who perceived work pressure might vent their frustrations on either the organization or organizational members. Hence:

H13: Self-control moderates the relationship between workload and organizational deviance. The relationship will be weaker (less positive) for individuals high in self-control than those low in self-control.

H14: Self-control moderates the relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance. The relationship will be weaker (less positive) for individuals high in self-control than those low in self-control.

H15: Self-control moderates the relationship between work pressure and organizational deviance. The relationship will be weaker (less positive) for individuals high in self-control than those low in self-control.

H16: Self-control moderates the relationship between work pressure and interpersonal deviance. The relationship will be weaker (less positive) for individuals high in self-control than those low in self-control.

Based on previous empirical studies and theories as presented in this study, we developed and tested a model in which self-control moderated the relationship between ethical climate, institutional policy, workload, work pressure and DWB. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework.

Theoretical Framework

General theory of crime

This study is guided by self-control theory of crime, also known as general theory of crime (Hirschi & Gottfredson, 1990) and social exchange theory (Blau, 1964). Self-control theory postulates that persons low in self-control may probably participate in delinquent behaviours, unethical and criminal acts than individuals with high level of self-control especially in the face of open opportunity to engage in deviance. The opportunity-related factors (ethical climate and perception of institutional policy) can be explained by theory of self-control because Hirschi and Gottfredson (1990) theorized that the single most important factor behind crime is individual lack of self-control. Therefore, criminal acts are often markedly non-controlled; they are both opportunistic and short-sighted. The theory posits that those low in self-control are more likely to engage in DWB unlike those who possess high level of self-control and who have the ability to suppress undesired behaviours. From managerial perspective, we argue that ethical climate and institutional policy are not sufficient to reduce negative deviance because human beings are innovative and will always innovate ways to outsmart organizational procedures. Hence, the level of self-control of an individual matter.

Social exchange theory (SET)

This study is equally located within social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), which explains the nature of work relationship between the employer and employees. Whenever the administrators of HEIs pressurized faculty members with excessive workload and work pressure on a continuous basis, there is tendency for academics to retaliate in form of negative deviance either towards the organization or colleagues/students. This may likely happen in the long-run when self-control resources of employees are depleted. In other words, social relationships are governed by norms of reciprocity (Blau, 1964), which simply states that people should return benefits or negative treatment given to them in a relationship.

Methods

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Sample and data collection

Using cluster sampling, data were collected through self-administered questionnaires from 536 faculty members in public HEIs. In all 413 participants (77%) were males while 123 participants (23%) were females. In terms of age, 39% of the participants aged 41-50 years, 34% aged 31-40 years, 21.1% of the participants aged 50 years and above while 5.9% of the participants aged 21-30 years. Educationally, 29.2% of the participants were first degree holders, 45.2% possessed Masters' degrees while 25.6% of the participants were doctorate degree holders. About 70% of the participants have spent 6 years and above on the job. Hierarchically, there were 67 Professors among the participants (12.4%), 69 Associate professors representing 12.9%, 108 senior lecturers (20.2%), 86 participants on lecturer I cadre representing 16% while other lower cadres accounted for 38.5% of the participants (206).

Measures

The researchers requested the participants to rate each item on a 5-point Likert scales ranging from '1=strongly disagree' to '5=strongly agree', '1=mostly false' to '5=completely true' or '1=never' to '5=always.' All the scales reported acceptable levels of internal reliability.

Deviant workplace behaviour

In order to suit HEIs in Nigeria, we adapted, and validated deviance scale by Bennett and Robinson (2000). The validation procedures recommended by Polit and Beck (2006) was observed. The original scale demonstrated internal reliability of 0.81 and 0.78 for organizational deviance and interpersonal deviance respectively (Bennett & Robinson, 2000). All items were scored on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *never*; 2 = *rarely*; 3 = *sometimes*; 4 = *often*; 5 = *always*).

Ethical climate

We adapted 7 items ($\alpha = 0.79$) from Schwepker and Hartline (2005) ethical climate scale. Participants indicated their perceptions of the ethical climate on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *mostly false* to 5 = *completely true*). It is one of the best ethical climate scales.

Institutional Policy (IP)

We assessed perception of institutional policy with 5 items ($\alpha = 0.73-0.82$) adapted from Comer, Machleit, and Lagace's (1989) measure of company policy. Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement on a 5-point scale (1 = *strongly disagree*; to 5 = *strongly agree*).

Workload

Workload was assessed with 8 items ($\alpha = 0.74$ to 0.78) adapted from Houston, Meyer and Paewei (2006) job demands scale. Participants were asked to indicate their perception of workload on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*).

Work Pressure (WP)

WP was assessed with 5 items ($\alpha = 0.73$ to 0.85) adapted from Karasek and Theorell's (1990) scale. All participants were requested to indicate their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*).

Self-control

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Participants chose among 5 alternatives ranging from ‘1’ “not at all” to ‘5’ “very much”. We assessed self-control with 6 items ($\alpha = 0.64$) from Turner and Piquero’s (2002) self-control scale.

Demographics

Participants responded to demographic variables by choosing from the alternatives provided in the scale covering participants’ profiles on age, gender, highest educational qualifications, length of service and marital status.

Analysis

SmartPLS-SEM 3.0 software was employed to test the theoretical model in the present study (Wold, 1985) because the model is complex with the introduction of a moderating variable. We acknowledge that PLS-SEM has an issue with assessment of model fit and potential lack of complete consistency in scores on latent variables (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014). Notwithstanding the limitations, proper procedural and statistical measures were taken to ensure validity of our results.

Results

In order to lessen common method variance (CMV), we computed Harman's single factor test which revealed that CMV is not an issue because the single factor test result explained 20.517% which is below the cut-off value of 50%. Assumptions of linearity, normality, and multicollinearity were not violated (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Thereafter, we observed two-step process namely measurement model and structural model (Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009).

Measurement model

Regarding the individual item reliability, Hair et al. (1998) opined that internal reliability value of 0.60 or more is considered to be significant. However, Hair et al. (2014) and Nunnally (1978) suggested 0.70 as the minimum for retaining items. The present study retained items with loadings 0.60 and above (Hair et al., 1998; Hair et al., 2013). Out of 59 items, 26 items were deleted because they presented loadings below 0.60 (Table 1). Also, the internal consistency reliability was assessed using composite reliability (CRI) (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena, 2012). Table 1 presents measurement model.

Table 1
Measurement Model Table

Constructs and Indicators	Loadings	Composite Reliability	AVE
Ethical climate		0.889	0.668
EC04	0.813		
EC05	0.830		
EC06	0.803		

EC07	0.821		
Institutional policy		0.909	0.666
IP01	0.813		
IP02	0.865		
IP03	0.872		
IP04	0.769		
IP05	0.753		
Workload		0.903	0.651
WL01	0.879		
WL02	0.884		
WL03	0.763		
WL05	0.768		
WL06	0.731		
Work pressure		0.883	0.715
WP01	0.899		
WP02	0.774		
WP04	0.858		
Self-control		0.906	0.618
SC01	0.757		
SC02	0.871		
SC03	0.898		
SC04	0.720		
SC05	0.749		
SC06	0.695		
Interpersonal deviance		0.948	0.819
ID01	0.829		

ID02	0.925		
ID03	0.930		
ID04	0.933		
Organizational deviance		0.886	0.564
OD01	0.671		
OD02	0.736		
OD03	0.787		
OD04	0.774		
OD05	0.783		
OD06	0.760		

Table 1 presents CRI values ranging from 0.883 to 0.948, all exceeded 0.70 as recommended by Bagozzi and Yi (1988). Similarly, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was computed to determine the convergent validity of the model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). From Table 1, all AVE values are greater than 0.50 (Chin, 1998) indicating adequate convergent validity. Figure 2 adds support to the values presented in Table 1.

Figure 2

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Measurement Model Graph

Also, Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) was computed to ascertain discriminant validity. Table 2 presents discriminant validity test using HTMT.

Table 2
Discriminant Validity - (Heterotrait-monotrait ratio)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Ethical climate							
2. Institutional policy	0.164						
3. Workload	0.707	0.228					
4. Work pressure	0.659	0.144	0.828				
5. Self-control	0.397	0.297	0.354	0.404			
6. Organisational deviance	0.105	0.512	0.207	0.138	0.294		
7. Interpersonal deviance	0.583	0.049	0.577	0.651	0.250	0.141	

Table 2 showed that all obtained correlation values are less than the lowest pre-defined threshold of 0.85, reflecting an acceptable level of HTMT in assessing discriminant validity (Kline, 2011; Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015).

4.2 Structural model

For the purpose of evaluating the path coefficients, bootstrapping procedures with 5,000 bootstrap samples and 536 cases were considered (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena, 2012).

Specifically, Table 3 revealed a significant negative relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance ($\beta=-0.251$; $t=3.966$; $p< 0.01$), supporting Hypothesis 2. Also, results supported a negative relationship between perception of institutional policy and organizational deviance ($\beta=-0.400$; $t=8.135$; $p< 0.01$), supporting Hypothesis 3. Findings showed that workload was positively related to interpersonal deviance ($\beta=0.108$; $t=1.510$; $p< 0.1$), suggesting support for hypothesis 6. Last but not the least, a significant positive relationship between work pressure and interpersonal deviance was reported ($\beta=0.353$; $t=3.915$; $p< 0.01$), suggesting support for hypothesis 8.

Table 3:
Structural Effect Model

Hypotheses	Relations	Beta	SE	t-value	p-value	Findings
H1	EC → OD	0.070	0.060	1.156	0.124	Not supported

H2	EC → ID	-0.251	0.063	3.966*	0.000	Supported	
H3	IP → OD	-0.400	0.049	8.135*	0.000	Supported	
H4	IP → ID	0.047	0.045	1.052	0.147	Not supported	
H5	Workload → OD	0.046	0.069	0.667	0.253	Not supported	
H6	Workload → ID	0.108	0.071	1.510***	0.066	Supported	
H7	Work pressure → OD	-0.028	0.072	0.394	0.347	Not supported	
H8	Work pressure → ID	0.353	0.090	3.915*	0.000	Supported	
H9	EC *Self-control → OD	0.158	0.137	1.152	0.125	Not supported	
H10	EC *Self-control → ID	0.326	0.139	2.342**	0.010	Supported	
H11	IP *Self-control → OD	-0.116	0.147	0.787	0.216	Not supported	
H12	IP *Self-control → ID	0.155	0.163	0.956	0.170	Not supported	
H13	WL *Self-control → OD	0.074	0.167	0.440	0.330	Not supported	
H14	WL *Self-control → ID	0.391	0.204	1.918**	0.028	Supported	
H15	WP *Self-control → OD	-0.137	0.144	0.956	0.170	Not supported	
H16	WP *Self-control → ID	-0.127	0.147	0.865	0.194	Not supported	
		ID	OD				
R^2 - Interpersonal deviance		45%	27.3%				
Q^2 - Organisational deviance		0.301	0.124				
SRMR		0.070					

Notes: *Significant at 0.01 (1-tailed), **Sig. at 0.05 (1-tailed) *Sig. at 0.1 (1-tailed).** EC= ethical climate, IP= institutional policy, WL= workload and WP = work pressure, Interp=interpersonal deviance, Org deviance= organizational deviance.

Having confirmed the significance of the path coefficients, we appraised the predictive relevance of the model, effect size and level of R -squared values. The present study explained 0.273 (27.3%) of the total variance in organizational deviance and 0.450 (45%) of interpersonal deviance. Both values are above 0.10, which is the minimum required R^2 value (Falk & Miller, 1992). Figure 3 presents the structural model graph.

Figure 3: Structural model graph

Effect size and predictive relevance

Effect size indicates the relative effect of a particular exogenous latent variable on endogenous latent variable(s) by means of changes in the R^2 (Chin, 1998). It is calculated as the increase in R^2 of the latent variable to which the path is connected, relative to the latent variable's proportion of unexplained variance (Cohen, 1988; Chin, 1998). The current SmartPLS 3.0 automatically generated effect size for the model as shown in Table 4.

Table 4
Effect Sizes (F^2)

	Organisational deviance	Interpersonal deviance
1. Ethical climate	0.003	0.064
2. Institutional policy	0.202	0.004
3. Workload	0.003	0.012
4. Work pressure	0.000	0.090

Effect size (f^2) values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 can be interpreted as small, medium, and large effects in that order. Results from table 4 showed varying degrees of effect sizes of the exogenous latent variables on

endogenous variables. Some can be considered as none (no effect), while others reported small and medium effect sizes.

Also, we applied blindfolding procedures in order to test the predictive ability of the model (Geisser, 1974; Stone, 1974) by a way of cross-validated redundancy measure- Q^2 (Geisser, 1974; Stone, 1974; Ringle et al., 2012). Chin (1998) and Hair et al. (2014) set three criteria for assessing Q^2 . First, Q^2 of 0.02 demonstrates that the model has small predictive relevance. Second, Q^2 of 0.15 demonstrates that the model has medium predictive relevance, while Q^2 of 0.35 demonstrates that the model has large predictive relevance. Generally, any model with Q^2 values greater than zero has adequate predictive relevance (Henseler et al., 2009). Results from table 3 revealed Q^2 values of 0.124 and 0.301 for organizational and interpersonal deviance respectively. Both values exceed zero and signify medium predictive relevance (Chin, 1998).

Moderating effects

We applied a product-indicator approach using PLS-SEM (Chin et al., 2003; Henseler & Fassott, 2010) to examine the strength of self-control as a moderator in the relationship between the dimensions of opportunity, job pressure and DWB. Firstly, we incorporated all the predictors (exogenous variables) including the moderator and considered them as independent variables in the model. Secondly, the latent interaction term was created by multiplying the products of each indicator of the exogenous latent variables with each indicator of the moderating variable (Henseler & Fassott, 2010). Thirdly, we estimated the standardized path coefficients to confirm whether the interaction effects are significant (see Table 3). Lastly, we ascertained the strength of the moderating effects.

Only H10 and H14 had significant interaction effects on the constructs (Table 3 and Figure 3). Hypothesis 10 predicted that self-control would moderate the relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance and this was supported ($\beta = 0.326$; $t = 2.342$; $p < 0.05$). Figure 4 portrays the relations between ethical climate and self-control in predicting interpersonal deviance. The interaction between ethical climate and self-control revealed higher positive feedback for persons who possess low level of self-control than employees who scored high in self-control. See Figure 4.

Figure 4

The interaction between ethical climate and self-control in predicting interpersonal deviance

Also, the results of interaction effect supported Hypothesis 14 significantly ($\beta = 0.391$; $t=1.918$; $p < 0.05$). This implies that individuals who are high in self-control will exercise restraints and engage less in interpersonal deviance than those who are low in self-control. Relatedly, Figure 5 illustrates the interactions between workload and self-control towards predicting interpersonal deviance.

Figure 5:
The interaction between workload and self-control in predicting interpersonal deviance

Moderating effect size (f^2)

The final aspect of analysis was to ascertain the strength of the moderation using Cohen’s (1988) effect size formula. Strength of moderation was assessed by comparing “the proportion of variance explained (as expressed by the determination coefficient- R^2) of the main effect model (i.e. the model without moderating effect) with the R^2 of the full model (i.e. the model including the moderating effect)” (Henseler & Fassott, 2010). Effect sizes (f^2) of 0.02 are weak, 0.15 moderate, and 0.35 strong (Cohen, 1988). Table 5 presents moderating effect size.

Table 5
Moderating Effect Size

R^2 Included	R^2 Excluded	f -squared	Effect size
0.542	0.496	0.100	Small

Following Cohen’s (1988) guideline, Table 5 indicates that the strength of the moderating effect of self-control on the constructs is 0.100, which suggests small effect size.

Discussion

The study's foremost aim was to ascertain the moderating effects of self-control on the relationship between ethical climate, institutional policy, workload, work pressure and DWB among academics in Nigerian HEIs. This study has enhanced self-control theory (general theory of crimes), social exchange theory and added to the extant literature on DWB. Results from the structural effect model (Table 3) showed that there was a significant negative relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance (H2). This implies that whenever academics in Nigeria perceive a sound ethical climate, the occurrence of interpersonal deviance will be minimal.

Similarly, the predicted negative relationship between institutional policy and organizational deviance was supported (H3). This implies that perception of effective institutional policy will mitigate organizational deviance, especially reward and punishment policy. This finding is supported by general deterrence theory (GDT) (Beccaria, 1963; Gibbs, 1968). GDT basically theorizes that if certainty of punishment for an unethical act is firm and assured, individuals will be dissuaded from participating in deviant acts because of the unpleasant experiences that accompany unethical behaviours. Also, past studies found that employees' decisions to act morally or unethically are significantly determined by stated policies (Cheng et al., 2013) and if these policies are well implemented in tertiary institutions, deviance will not thrive.

Furthermore, results revealed positive relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance (H6). Also, results indicated a positive relationship between pressure of work and interpersonal deviance (H8). This finding is supported by job control model (Karasek, 1979), which posits that job pressure is positively related to strain with tendency to result in interpersonal deviance.

Next, the moderating effect of self-control was examined. Self-control moderated the relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance in positive direction (H10). The results showed that low level of self-control increases interpersonal deviance when there is weakness in ethical climate of HEIs. Also, findings revealed that self-control moderated the positive relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance (H 14). Specifically, self-control diminishes the positive relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance. Theory of self-control (Gottfredson & Hirschi, 1990) and past empirical studies supported this finding (H14) because people with high level of self-control have been found to be less aggressive toward others at work and less likely to perform counterproductive behaviors (Bordia, Restubog, & Tang, 2008).

Theoretical implication

The present study offers theoretical implications empirically in the domains of general theory of crime (also known as theory of self-control) and social exchange theory. The general theory of crime postulates that persons low in self-control might participate in delinquent behaviours, unethical, deviant and criminal acts than individuals who scored high in self-control especially in the face of open opportunity to engage in unethical acts. This study extends general theory of crime by assessing opportunity-related factors in predicting DWB among lecturers in Nigerian higher educational institutions (HEIs). While testing general theory of crimes, findings revealed a significant negative relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance. Similarly, negative relationship between perception of institutional policy and organizational deviance was supported. Also, using social exchange theory, the study revealed a positive relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance among lecturers and a positive relationship between pressure of work and interpersonal deviance. Therefore, it is important to consider ethical climate,

perception of institutional policy, workload, work pressure and lecturers' level of self-control to ensure positive work behaviours.

Practical implications

Although ethical climate, perception of institutional policy, workload and work pressure are predictors of deviant behaviour in the present study, there is need for personality tests focused on self-control during recruitment exercise to identify applicants with high level of self-control, who would refrain from unethical acts. This is because self-control moderated the relationship between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance and moderated the relationship between workload and interpersonal deviance.

Organizational interventions aimed at reducing DWB need to evaluate the ethical climate and policies of HEIs in Nigeria and review the existing workloads of academics. Recently, a country-based report found that about 70% of public HEIs in Nigeria are understaffed with resultant effects on academics in form of excessive workload (NEEDS Report, 2012). Therefore, our findings agreed with this report that workload can trigger interpersonal deviance, hence, there is need to review academic workloads in Nigeria.

Limitations and Future research directions

The following constraints and guides for future researchers should be considered when interpreting the results of the present study. First, the cross-sectional nature of the present study implies that the findings have limited generalization. Hence, this study needs to be replicated using longitudinal research to allow for causal inferences. Secondly, the sample was drawn from lecturers in public tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, we suggest that future researchers should include faculty members in private HEIs in order to generalize their findings. Thirdly, future researchers should consider other moderating variables such as integrity and conscientiousness.

Finally, DWB was assessed using self-report measures. It is important to note that the use of self-reports is associated with common method variance (Podsakoff & Organ, 1986) but we took both procedural and statistical remedies to minimize bias (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2012). However, future researchers should consider the use of peer-rating in order to control common method bias.

Conclusion

The findings indicated that self-control moderated the relationships between ethical climate and interpersonal deviance and between workload and interpersonal deviance. Self-control is a veritable tool to restrain deviant acts even when there are opportunities and pressure to engage in negative deviance. Therefore, management of HEIs in Nigeria are encouraged to create a sound ethical climate, effective institutional policies and conduct holistic reviews of faculty members' workload with a view to minimize negative deviance among lecturers.

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